

ThrombUS+ Data Management Plan

Version 0

Description

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on a novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally. Various data sets, including ultrasound images from five clinical studies will be collected during the ThrombUS+. This document serves as the Data Management Plan for all these data sets.

ThrombUS+ project:

Grant Agreement: 101137227

Start date: January 1st, 2024

End date: June 30th, 2027

Funder

European Commission||EC

Grant

ThrombUS+: Wearable
Continuous Point-of-Care
Monitoring, Risk Estimation
and Prevention for Deep Vein
Thrombosis/ No 101137227

Researchers

Organizations

ECHONOUS INC, MEDIS MEDIZINISCHE MESSTECHNIK GMBH,
COMFTECH SRL, Fraunhofer Institute for Photonic
Microsystems, Technologija, Kaunas University of Technology,
FONDAZIONE CASA SOLLIEVO DELLA SOFFERENZA,
PREDICTBY RESEARCH AND CONSULTING S.L., SCIGEN
TECHNOLOGIES ANONYMI ETAIREIA PARAGOGIS LOGISMIKOU
KAI ILEKTROMICHANOLOGIKON KATASKEUON, VERMON SA,
MEDEA SRL, VDE VERBAND DER ELEKTROTECHNIK
ELEKTRONIK INFORMATIONSTECHNIK EV, GROUPEMENT
HOSPITALIER EAUBONNE MONTMORENCY SIMONE VEIL,
PHAZE KLINIKI EREVNA & FARMAKEFTIKES SYMVOULES
ANONYMI ETAIREIA, UZDAROJI AKCINE BENDROVE TELEMED,
Lithuanian University of Health Sciences, Athena Research
and Innovation Center In Information Communication &
Knowledge Technologies, GENIKO NOSOKOMEIO
PAPAGEORGIU, TAMPEREEN KORKEAKOULUSAATIO SR

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [ThrombUS+ Data Management Plan](#)

Description:

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on a novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally. Various data sets, including ultrasound images from five clinical studies will be collected during the ThrombUS+. This document serves as the Data Management Plan for all these data sets.

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GENIKO NOSOKOMEIO PAPAGEORGIU
TAMPEREEN KORKEAKOULUSAATIO SR

Contact: Stylianos Didaskalou

2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission||EC

Grants: ThrombUS+: Wearable Continuous Point-of-Care Monitoring, Risk Estimation and Prevention for Deep Vein Thrombosis

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

ThrombUS+ Clinical Study A Dataset: Conventional ultrasound image/video sets collected from patients referred on suspicion of DVT of lower limb.

Ultrasound images and video clips collected from patients referred on suspicion of DVT. The dataset also contains patient demographics, biometrics and related medical history data and diagnosis. Finally image/video data is accompanying by

the output of labelling by experts to identify structures relevant to DVT diagnosis. Data sets from 3000 patients (with or without DVT) are planned.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Diagnostic medical images and videos collected during routine conventional ultrasound scan on suspicion of DVT of the lower limb.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Data collected will comprise of:

-DICOM images/video and related data

-Patient demographics, biometrics and medical history in JSON format, including mappings to SNOMED-CT, ICD-11, and any other appropriate medical terminology or vocabulary.

Processed data sets will include:

-Anonymized images and videos in a lossless commonly used format (e.g. tiff).

-Patient demographics, biometrics and medical history in JSON including mappings to SNOMED-CT, ICD-11, and any other appropriate medical terminology or vocabulary

-Image/video labeling data in JSON format.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

200GB or more

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To develop a product

Training AI models

Use for training and science awareness via open data challenge

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data collected from patients referred for an ultrasound scan on suspicion of DVT in the respective department of the 5 participating hospitals in ThrombUS+ consortium, namely:

- Tampere University Hospital (Finland),
- Lithuanian University of Health Science (Lithuania),
- Papageorgiou General Hospital (Greece),
- Home Relief of Suffering Hospital (Italy), and
- Simon Veil Hospital (France).

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Education
- Industry

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

1. DataCite Schema for data description.
2. SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records.

3. ICD, International Classification of Diseases.

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

a. https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf

b. <https://www.snomed.org/>

c. <https://icd.who.int/en/>

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Metadata are indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing, and are also automatically linked to the OpenAIRE graph.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

Deep vein thrombosis, ultrasound image, ultrasound video, lower limb.

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

Via Zenodo, metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API.

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

If the dataset is larger than 200 GB (which is the upper limit for Zenodo in extraordinary cases, 50 GB normally), data will be split or other infrastructure will be considered (e.g. paid option in FigShare <https://figshare.com/>)

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Assigns PIDs
- Follows metadata standards
- Follows curation processes
- Supports authentication and authorization of users
- Has data security mechanisms in place

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

N/A

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

DOI

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

To be decided

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

Yes

Zenodo

3.2.2.6 Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.

Zenodo's REST API

3.2.2.7 Please provide information about the tools needed to access the dataset / output.

Internet connection and a browser

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Open

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Definitely

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite provides relevant fields.

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

DataCite Schema for data description https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf

SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records
<https://www.snomed.org/>

ICD, International Classification of Diseases, <https://icd.who.int/en/>

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

N/A

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

Using common standards and format where appropriate.

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

Widely used medical standards, controlled vocabularies and terminologies.

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

Medical controlled vocabularies are mapped and crosslinked via UMLS.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

- Creative Commons Attribution 4.0
- CC0 1.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Readme files

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Promote via data challenges.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

The data will be collected via clinical study protocol approved via Ethics Committees. The protocol ID will be provided.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

5000

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

- Security

Direct cost

Part of the cost for WP7 and WP8 of ThrombUS+ project.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

ThrombUS+ project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

- a. Eleni Kaldoudi (orcid:0000-0002-6054-4961)

ThrombUS+ Coordinator

Role: High level management of the data set

- b. Stylianos Didaskalou (orcid:0000-0001-5932-9626)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

ThrombUS+ Project Manager

Role: Technical management of the data set

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

None

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

N/A

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Via publication in Zenodo

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

Data will be collected via a clinical study protocol approved by relevant ethics committees and after informed consent.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements

Yes

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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